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OPENMIN Project

Deliverable Number 2.3

Creating new post-harmonized datasets for the Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Post-harmonized Survey Data Bank

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Introduction

This document is a deliverable of the OPENMIN project, *“Consolidating Open Science and Data Initiatives on Ethnic and Migrant Minorities in Europe.”* It outlines the developments made to the [Ethnic and Migrant Minorities \(EMM\) Post-Harmonized Survey Data Bank](#) over the course of the project, within the framework of Task 2.3. This task built on workflow processes previously developed under the COST Action ETHMIGSURVEYDATA to create three cross-national post-harmonized survey datasets for the pilot version of the Bank.: (1) civic and political integration of minorities, (2) discrimination against minorities, and (3) Ukrainian refugee surveys.

The EMM Post-Harmonized Survey Data Bank aims to facilitate the reuse of independently produced surveys by integrating them into a set of single, standardized datasets. The post-harmonization procedures are fully documented in publicly accessible Stata code, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and comparability across the pooled datasets. The overarching goal is to enhance the reuse of survey data and to improve the accuracy and comparability of knowledge on the economic, social, and political integration and inclusion of EMMs across Europe.

A first pilot on EMM survey data post-harmonization was carried out within WP3 of [CA16111-ETHMIGSURVEYDATA COST Action](#), in collaboration with the ANR-funded [FAIRETHMIGQUANT](#) project and the Swiss National Science Foundation project *‘Is the Integration of Muslim Migrants More Difficult? Unpacking the Differences of the Social, Economic, Civic, and Political Integration of Muslim and Non-Muslim Migrants in Switzerland in Comparative Perspective’*. This pilot led to the development of a post-harmonization workflow and tested its feasibility using a number of locally conducted surveys focusing on migrants’ social ties and civic participation.

Methodology

The EMM Post-Harmonized Survey Data Bank pools quantitative surveys conducted among EMM (sub)populations that meet the following criteria:

- Fielded since at least January 2000;
- Conducted in at least one of the countries covered by the EMM Survey Registry (see the full list of countries here); and

To produce each post-harmonized survey dataset, the following main steps are undertaken:

1. Identifying surveys for inclusion;
2. Specifying target variables;
3. Identifying question items corresponding to the target variables;
4. Obtaining data matrices;
5. Constructing target variable measures and the accompanying codebook; and
6. Building the post-harmonized dataset and documenting data transformations using Stata do-files.

Detailed information on the methodology used to produce and add surveys to the collection is provided in Appendix 1 of this document, titled *“Pilot 1 – Civic & Political Engagement Data Post-Harmonization Workflow.”*

Post-harmonized datasets

A. Surveys on migrants' civic and political participation - local level

The dataset postharmonizes and pools the following surveys:

1. **LOCALMULTIDEM: Multicultural Democracy and Immigrants' Social Capital in Europe: Participation, Organisational Networks, and Public Policies at the Local Level (2004–2008)**

This is a cross-national, individual-level survey conducted between 2004 and 2008 across ten major European cities: Budapest (HU), London (UK), Lyon (FR), Milan (IT), Barcelona and Madrid (ES), Geneva and Zurich (CH), Stockholm (SE), and Oslo (NO). In subsequent years, two additional waves were carried out in two more cities, Brussels (BE) in 2009 by Barbara Herman and Turin (IT) in 2014 by Zakaria Sajir, using, to a great extent, the same methodology and questionnaire as the original survey.

Data citation(s):

- Morales, Laura; Anduiza, Eva; Bengtsson, Bo; Cinalli, Manlio; Diani, Mario; Giugni, Marco; Orkeny, Antal; Rogstad, Jon; Statham, Paul, 2014, "LOCALMULTIDEM and MDE Individual Survey (WP4) Dataset, 2004-2008", Harvard Dataverse, V5, UNF:6:yecNYyqTj8fnNh4PvSohA== [fileUNF]
- Sajir, Zakaria, 2017, "Individual-level Survey – Moroccan-origin Community of Turin", <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/3MRMUR>, Harvard Dataverse, V2

2. **Immigrant Citizens Survey (ICS)**

The Immigrant Citizens Survey (ICS) was conducted in 15 European cities, including Antwerp, Brussels, and Liège in Belgium; Lyon and Paris in France; Berlin and Stuttgart in Germany; Budapest in Hungary; Milan and Naples in Italy; Faro, Lisbon, and Setúbal in Portugal; and Barcelona and Madrid in Spain.

The project was jointly coordinated by the King Baudouin Foundation and the Migration Policy Group.

3. **The integration of the Second Generation (TIES)**

Project coordinators:

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Schoorl, Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI); Barbara Herzog Punzenberger, Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW); Karen Phalet and Marc Swyngedouw, The Center for Sociological Research and Methodology, University of Leuven; Patrick Simon and Christelle Hamel, Institut National d'Etudes Démographique (INED); Charles Westin, Alireza Behtoui and Ali Osman, Centre for Research in International Migration and Ethnic Relations (CEIFO), Stockholm University; Maren Wilmes and Michael Bommers, Institute for Migration Research and Intercultural Studies (IMIS), Osnabrück University

7 national-level datasets were pooled and post-harmonized for TIES:

- Austria
- Belgium
- France
- Germany
- Netherlands
- Sweden
- Switzerland

Data citations (for publicly available datasets through a data archive):

- a. TIES-NL: N.E. Hornstra; G. Groenewold; L. Lessard-Phillips, 2007, "The Integration of the European Second Generation in Amsterdam and Rotterdam (TIES-NL), 2006-2007.", <https://doi.org/10.17026/DANS-ZKK-W38F>, DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities, V4, UNF:6:lg/yKrr1ownR8nnXBWudwA== [fileUNF]
- b. TIES-DE: Pott, A. (2014). The Integration of the European Second Generation in Frankfurt and Berlin (TIES Germany) – reduced version (ZA5616; Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. GESIS, Cologne. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.11897>

4. Electoral Participation of Immigrants in the Local Elections of the Canton of Geneva

Data citation(s):

- Didier Ruedin, Rosita Fibbi Carton: Participation politique des immigrants dans le canton de Genève – 2015 [Dataset]. Université de Neuchâtel – Faculté des lettres et des sciences humaines – Forum suisse pour l'étude des migrations et de la population – SFM. Distributed by FORS, Lausanne, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.23662/FORS-DS-814-1>
- Ruedin, Didier, 2016, "Electoral Participation of Immigrants in the Local Elections of the Canton of Geneva, Switzerland in 2015", <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/QEMYEB>, Harvard Dataverse, V4, UNF:6:mN2B1yqBH72WLQJ+3mKn/Q== [fileUNF]

5. Duisburg Citizens Survey (2004 wave)

Data citation: Stadt Duisburg, Amt für Statistik, Stadtforschung und Europaangelegenheiten (2007). Duisburg Citizen Survey (Autumn 2004, Foreign population) (ZA4522; Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. GESIS, Cologne. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.4522>

6. Duisburg Citizens Survey (2006 wave)

Data citation: Stadt Duisburg, Amt für Statistik, Stadtforschung und Europaangelegenheiten (2007). Duisburg Citizen Survey (Autumn 2006, Foreign population) (ZA4524; Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. GESIS, Cologne. <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.4524>

B. Surveys on migrants' civic and political participation - national level

Once the post-harmonization of the local-level surveys on migrants' civic and political incorporation was completed, we initiated the same process — following the same methodology — for the post-harmonization of several national-level surveys that also focus on civic and political incorporation, notably:

- The five waves of the [Swiss Migration and Mobility Survey](#) (2016–2024)
- The 2010 [Ethnic Minority British Election Study \(EMBES\)](#) survey in the UK
- The two waves of the [French TeO \(TeO1 and TeO2\)](#)
- The two waves of the [Immigrant German Election Study \(IMGES\) surveys](#) (2017 and 2021)
- The [Dutch Ethnic Minority Election Study \(DEMES\) 2021](#) survey
- The [2015–2016 Second European Union minorities and discrimination survey](#) (EU-MIDIS II)

In addition, we plan to include — subject to data access — the Norwegian electoral surveys of voters with an immigrant background ([2013](#), [2015](#), and [2017](#)).

C. Surveys on discrimination against minorities

We have also made substantial progress in the post-harmonization of surveys on discrimination against minorities, reaching the third step of this process (i.e., identifying question items corresponding to the target variables). In particular, we have identified and included the following national-level surveys in this collection:

- The two waves of the [French TeO \(TeO1 and TeO2\)](#)
- The [2015–2016 Second European Union minorities and discrimination survey](#) (EU-MIDIS II)
- The five waves of the [Swiss Migration and Mobility Survey](#) (2016–2024)
- The two waves of the [Causes and Consequences of Socio-Cultural Integration Processes among New Immigrants in Europe \(SCIP\)](#) project
- The 2010 [Ethnic Minority British Election Study \(EMBES\)](#) survey in the UK
- The [Migrants' Experiences of Racism and Xenophobia in 12 EU Member States \(pilot study\)](#)
- The [Cultural Interactions between Muslim Immigrants and Receiving Societies \(EURISLAM\)](#)

Further progress is expected in the coming months, up to May 2026, when the project formally concludes for Kozminski University, the partner responsible for leading this collection.

D. Ukrainian refugee surveys

For this collection, several efforts were undertaken to obtain access to a selected number of survey datasets targeting Ukrainian refugees who left Ukraine following the Russian invasion in February 2022. To this end, multiple data producers and data owners were contacted. However, because many of these surveys had been fielded very recently, survey producers from academia were reluctant to share the datasets for this purpose. In parallel, we also contacted several national and international organizations and EU agencies, but with similarly limited success.

Some examples are outlined below. The European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA) was contacted to request access to the [Survey of Arriving Migrants from Ukraine \(SAM-UKR\)](#), rounds 1 and 2. While EUAA agreed to share the survey questionnaire, access to the underlying microdata was not granted. The Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) was also contacted, but indicated that they were unable to provide access to the [Online Survey on Persons Displaced from Ukraine](#) that they conducted. Similarly, UNHCR was contacted regarding the [Socio-Economic Insights Survey \(SEIS\)](#). Although UNHCR shared the dataset, they did not agree to its use for post-harmonization with other survey datasets. The International Organization for Migration (IOM) was also contacted regarding [surveys conducted with refugees from Ukraine](#); however, no response was received despite several contact attempts. Finally, the IMPACT Initiatives team was contacted about the [Longitudinal Survey of Ukrainian Refugees](#), but without success, as they stated that respondent-level microdata would not be made publicly available. This decision was based on concerns that even anonymised data could allow identification, given the detailed longitudinal tracking of families' geographic, socio-economic, and other characteristics.

Lastly, with regard to the [IAB-BAMF-SOEP Survey of Refugees](#), after prolonged negotiations, we were only able to obtain consent to share the Stata code used for post-harmonization with the other datasets, without permission to redistribute any anonymized microdata. Under these conditions, unfortunately, it is unlikely that further progress on this specific collection can be achieved within the duration of the project.

Publication/Dissemination of the post-harmonized datasets

The cross-national, post-harmonized datasets will be disseminated via Zenodo and/or the Harvard Dataverse, and potentially also through CESSDA-affiliated archives. We are currently exploring the most appropriate option, with a final decision expected by January 2026.

Aggregated results from these datasets will also be showcased on the EMM Survey Data Playground, a newly launched platform developed within the OPENMIN project.

Appendix 1. Civic & Political Engagement: Data Post-Harmonization Workflow

Civic & Political Engagement: Data Post Harmonization Workflow

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Introduction

This document outlines the workflow for the post-harmonization of survey data on migrants' civic and political participation at the local and national levels. It was developed as part of WP3 of COST Action CA16111 (ETHMIGSURVEYDATA), through work undertaken jointly by the ANR-funded FAIRETHMIGQUANT project and the Swiss National Science Foundation-funded project *"Is the Integration of Muslim Migrants More Difficult? Unpacking the Differences of the Social, Economic, Civic and Political Integration of Muslim and Non-Muslim Migrants in Switzerland in Comparative Perspective."* The work was completed within Task 2.3 of the CHIST-ERA-funded project OPENMIN, *"Consolidating Open Science and Data Initiatives on Ethnic and Migrant Minorities in Europe,"* in 2025.

The work has been segmented into surveys fielded at the local and national levels. Although only the work on the local-level surveys has been completed to date, the steps described herein apply to both levels unless otherwise specified.

People worked on this project

This work was overseen by Laura Morales, in collaboration with Katia Pilati.

Natalia Malancu, Meredith Winn, and Dimitrios-Rafail Tservenis contributed to the data post-harmonization as part of their respective postdoctoral research positions.

Carles Pamies, Alejandro Ciordia, Emma Lancha Hernández, and Zeynep Montesoglu participated through support for Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSMs) funded by COST Action CA16111. Hereafter, they are referred to as STSMs.

Step 1: Identifying surveys for inclusion

This work was undertaken by a team of STSMs, coordinated by Laura Morales, with contributions from Natalia Malancu.

We distinguished between (a) sub-national/local- and (b) national-level surveys. The same set of filters was applied to the [EMM Survey Registry](#) to identify surveys at either level. The filters were applied in the following order:

- A. Scope/level of survey (1.5)
- B. Adult respondents (1.15)
- C. Coverage of the topic *"Political inclusion and participation, and social/political attitudes"* (1.13.20)
- D. Availability of information on respondents' country of birth (3.3.1 or 3.4.1)
- E. Availability of information on respondents' (current) nationality/citizenship (3.3.3 or 3.4.4)
- F. Data publicly available, available by request, or available through a COST Action member (8.1)

- To cast a wider net of surveys, additional searches were conducted, excluding filters on country of birth and nationality/citizenship.
- For surveys available by request, the final decision on inclusion was based on the expediency of the request procedure and whether access involved a fee.
- In some cases, although data were available, additional effort was required to locate accompanying documentation. No surveys were excluded on this basis.

Step 2: Specifying target variables

In the first stage, Natalia Malancu, under the direction of Laura Morales, used the conceptual matrix developed by the Pilot 1-related working mini-group to specify the target variables needed to carry out the post-harmonization on civic and political integration (see [Appendix 1](#)). Specifically, the target variables were divided into the following large blocks: identification variables, outcome variables (civic and political engagement), outcome-model variables (socio-economic and demographic), and other relevant variables (religion-focused attitudinal and behavioral). Subsequently, the list of both outcome variables and outcome-model variables was expanded (i.e., added outcome variables referred to turnout, party preference, intention to vote, media consumption, interest in politics, while added outcome-model variables referred to various types of sociopolitical attitudes and opinions).

Step 3: Identifying question items corresponding to target variables

- This work was undertaken with a team of STSMs, Natalia Malancu, Meredith Winn, and directed by Laura Morales and Katia Pilati.
- For each survey identified as part of the pilot, we obtain every possible version of the questionnaire (including translated versions).
- Each person was assigned a set of questionnaires to review. Each questionnaire was read in its entirety, and each question corresponding to a target variable was indicated on a Harmonization Sheet.
 - Whenever possible, STSM participants were assigned questionnaires in languages they spoke. However, some questionnaires were available only in languages not spoken by any team member. In these cases, Google Translate was used. It should be noted that such translations were always conducted from a Master Questionnaire written in a language in which the reviewer was proficient to ensure consistency.

Step 4: Obtaining data matrices

All data matrices were accessed free of charge. Whenever possible, they were accessed from the data owners' and/or producers' websites (as indicated in the EMM Survey Registry) without any additional contact. If needed, Natalia Malancu, Meredith Winn, or one of the STSMs working on data harmonization, contacted the data owners and or producers in order to gain access. The request-based process of gaining access to the matrices was slower during summer (for obvious reasons), yet it never exceeded a total duration of more than three weeks.

Step 5: Building the target variable measures and codebook

- For each target variable identified in the Harmonization Sheet, a corresponding entry is made in the Harmonization Codebook¹. The variables in the codebook have been divided into 12 thematic sections, roughly corresponding to concepts identified by WG3 for the conceptual hierarchy (see [Appendix 2](#))
- STSMs assisting in post-harmonization were asked to include the following information based on the response options found in the questionnaires:
 - Variable label: the variable label defined in the Harmonization Sheet
 - Variable name: A brief, descriptive name. Where possible, these were to remain under 20 characters.
 - Variable description: Describing what the variable intends to measure in 1-2 lines
 - Type: Numeric or String
 - Scale: For numeric variables, describe whether it is continuous, interval, dichotomous, or categorical
 - Values: The value codes. For interval variables, this is the high and low values; for categorical variables, it includes the label for each discrete value, etc.
- To determine values, STSMs were asked to convert scales to intervals and find the best possible correspondence for categorical variables. Difficult cases were discussed with the team as a whole to find a solution
- The Codebook contains detailed instructions for filling in the document and formatting each variable. This information is also included in [Appendix 3](#).

Step 6: Building a post-harmonized dataset and documenting data transformation

- Stata do-files are used to document the data post-harmonization and the specific codes necessary to transform the data.
- The do-files are organized by the target variables, with each target variable or group of target variables being organized into its own do-file.
- The detailed instructions for creating these do-files can be found in the Stata do-file instructions (see [Appendix 4](#)). This process is summarized below:
 - A [formatted do-file](#) was created that shows the basic structure for formatting the do-files and includes: Do-file title, variable name and label, and how to annotate.
 - The final do-file name follows this naming convention: Section Name_Sub-section name (if there is one)_the coders' initials_date
 - The formula for rescaling ordinal variables is specified
 - An order for the codes that change the variable is specified
- The do-files are uploaded to the shared Google Drive folder named "Preliminary do-files".
- The "Existing Do-file" column in the Harmonisation sheet is marked "Yes" if a Do-file has been created for that variable. It is marked "N/A" if the targeted variable was not identified in any of the original datasets, and a Do-file was not required
- The preliminary do-files were reviewed by Natalia Malancu and Dimitrios Rafail Tservenis for errors, problems, or inconsistencies. When this review is completed, the column "Reviewed do-file" is marked as "Yes" to indicate that the review is complete.
- The preliminary do-files are used to generate a Master do-file that is used to create the final data matrix for use in analysis.

¹ Find the Harmonization Codebook in the following Zenodo record:

As an important note, initially, the CharmStats software, produced by GESIS, was considered for documenting data post-harmonization and generating codes for the transformations. After trialling the software, we decided not to use it because it was considered not flexible enough for the needs of this project.

Appendix 1: Conceptual matrix of pilot 1

Broader concept	Concept class	Narrower sub-concept (for types of indicators)
Civic & Associational involvement	Organizational membership	Membership
Civic & Associational involvement	Organizational engagement	activities performed - volunteer (unpaid) work
Civic & Associational involvement	Organizational engagement	activities performed - donations
Civic & Associational involvement	Level of engagement /forms of enagement	participation in decision-making
Civic & Associational involvement	Level of engagement /forms of enagement	chair/plan meeting
Civic & Associational involvement	Level of engagement /forms of enagement	give speech
Civic & Associational involvement	Level of engagement /forms of enagement	write text
Civic & Associational involvement	Duration of engagement	duration of membership in organization
Civic & Associational involvement	Duration of engagement	time spent in activities
Civic & Associational involvement	Type of organisation of membership	type of organisation
Civic & Associational involvement	Type of organisation of membership	activities orientated towards minority/ethnic group
Civic & Associational involvement	Type of organisation of membership	ethnicity of majority of members
Civic & Associational involvement	Type of organisation of membership	ethnic organisation
Civic & Associational involvement	Relevance of membership	importance of membership in respondent's life
Civic & Associational involvement	Relevance of membership	beginning of involvement (how it started)
Civic & Associational involvement	Relevance of membership	reason for non-involvement
Civic & Associational involvement	Relevance of membership	friends involved in organisations
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (retrospective) / Turnout	voted in last municipal elections in host country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (retrospective) / Turnout	voted in last national elections in host country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (retrospective) / Turnout	voted in last EU elections in host country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (retrospective) / Turnout	voted in last municipal elections in home country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (retrospective) / Turnout	voted in last national elections in home country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (retrospective) / Turnout	voted in last EU elections in home country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (prospective) / Turnout	intention to vote in municipal elections in host country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (prospective) / Turnout	intention to vote in national elections in host country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (prospective) / Turnout	intention to vote in EU elections in host country

Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (prospective) / Turnout	intention to vote (from abroad) in municipal elections in home country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (prospective) / Turnout	intention to vote (from abroad) in national elections in home country
Electoral behaviour	Electoral participation (prospective) / Turnout	intention to vote (from abroad) in EU elections in home country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote recall)	party voted for at national level in host country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote recall)	party voted for at local level in host country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote recall)	party voted for at EU level in host country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote recall)	party voted for at local level in home country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote recall)	party voted for at national level in home country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote recall)	party voted for at EU level in home country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote intention)	party choice intention for at national level in host country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote intention)	party choice intention at local level in host country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote intention)	party choice intention at EU level in host country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote intention)	party choice intention at local level in home country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote intention)	party choice intention at national level in home country
Electoral behaviour	Vote choice (vote intention)	party choice intention at EU level in home country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to vote	right to vote at local level in host country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to vote	right to vote at national level in host country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to vote	right to vote at EU level in host country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to vote	right to vote from abroad at local level in home country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to vote	right to vote from abroad at national level in home country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to vote	right to vote from abroad at EU level in home country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to run for office	right to vote at local level in host country
Electoral participation - behaviour	right to run for office	right to vote at national level in host country
Electoral participation - behaviour	run for office (retrospective)	ever ran for office in host country at local level
Electoral participation - behaviour	run for office (retrospective)	ever ran for office in host country at national level
Electoral participation - behaviour	run for office (prospective)	plans to run for office in host country at local level
Electoral participation - behaviour	run for office (prospective)	plans to run for office in host country at national level
Electoral participation - behaviour	wearing party badge	wearing party badge
Electoral participation - behaviour	ideological position	left.right position
Electoral participation - behaviour	party membership	member of political party
Electoral participation - behaviour	online activism	'liked' or 'followed' a political campaign on the internet
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with ethnic group
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people from same religion

Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (HOST COUNTRY) people
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people in neighbourhood
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people with the same sex/gender
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (HOST REGION) people
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (CITY)
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people of the same age
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with a particular social class
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with European people)
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with the world / humanity as a whole
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (HOME COUNTRY)
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with ethnic group
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people from same religion
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (HOST COUNTRY) people
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people in neighbourhood
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people with the same sex/gender
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (HOST REGION) people
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (CITY)
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with people of the same age
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with a particular social class
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with European people)
Identity	Self-identification	Self identification with (HOME COUNTRY)
Non-electoral political behaviour	Political participation (legal) / Institutional Part.	sign petitions (paper or online)
Non-electoral political behaviour	Political participation (legal) / Political Protest	participation in lawful demonstrations
Non-electoral political behaviour	Political participation (legal) / Political Protest	join boycott
Non-electoral political behaviour	Political participation (legal) / Institutional Part.	contact politicians
Non-electoral political behaviour	Political participation (illegal) / Political Protest	civil disobedience
Non-electoral political behaviour	Political participation (illegal) / Political Protest	participation in unlawful demonstrations
Non-electoral political behaviour	Political participation (illegal) / Political Protest	participation in sit-ins
Political attitudes	Political trust	Trust institutions
Political Engagement (Orientations)	Leaders Evaluations/Sympathy	Party Leader Evaluations
Political Engagement (Orientations)	Leaders Evaluations/Sympathy	Presidential candidates Evaluations
Political Engagement / Orientations	Political Confidence	Political Confidence National (Civil Service)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Political Confidence	Political Confidence National (Police)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Political Confidence	Political Confidence National (Politicians)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Political Confidence	Political Confidence Regional (Regional government)

Political Engagement / Orientations	Political Confidence	Political Confidence Local (Civil Servants & Public employees)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Political Confidence	Political Confidence European (EU, European Institutions)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Political Confidence	Political Confidence International & Supranational (United Nations)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Internal Political Efficacy	Internal Political Efficacy
Political Engagement / Orientations	External Political Efficacy	External Political Efficacy (General)
Political Engagement / Orientations	External Political Efficacy	External Political Efficacy (National)
Political Engagement / Orientations	External Political Efficacy	External Political Efficacy (Local)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Party Identification	Party Identification (support a party)
Political Engagement / Orientations	Party Identification	Party Sympathy (feeling close to one party)
Political Evaluations / Orientations	Ideological placements of parties	Left-Right Party Placements
Political Orientations	Political Legitimacy	Legitimacy of the political regime (Host Country)
Political Orientations	Political Legitimacy	Legitimacy of the political regime (Home Country)
Political Orientations	Satisfaction with Democracy	Legitimacy of the political regime (Home Country)
Political Orientations	Ideological Self-Placement	Left-Right Self-Placement
Political Orientations	National Identification	Attachment/ Feelings of belonging to the HOST COUNTRY
Political Orientations	National Identification	Identification with the HOME COUNTRY
Social attitudes	Trust	Trust in people (GENERAL)
Social attitudes	Trust	Trust in [RESPONDENT's ETHNIC GROUP] people
Social ties	Personal networks	People with whom RESP talk and interact frequently: What relationship
Social ties	Personal networks	People with whom RESP talk and interact frequently: Frequency of contact
Social ties	Personal networks	People with whom RESP talk and interact frequently: ethnic/national group
Social ties	Personal networks	People with whom RESP talk and interact frequently: frequency of political discussion
Social ties	Personal networks	Support network: who would RESP first ask for help/BORROW MONEY
Social ties	Personal networks	Support network: who would RESP first ask for help/FEELING DISCRIMINATED AGAINST
Social ties	Personal networks	Support network: who would RESP first ask for help/BEING DENIED HEALTH ASSISTANCE
Social ties	Personal networks	Support network: who would RESP first ask for help/NEED FOR LEGAL ASSISTANCE
Social ties	Transnational ties	Frequency of visits to HOME country/country of ancestors
Social ties	Transnational ties	Frequency of sending money HOME
Social ties	Personal networks	Having friends from same ethnic/minority group as RESPONDENT (YES/NO)
Social ties	Personal networks	Having friends from general/majority population (YES/NO)
Social ties	Personal networks	Having friends who have a different religion than Respondent
Social ties	Personal networks	Having relatives living in the same city

Social ties	Personal networks	Having relatives living in other European countries
Social ties	Personal networks	Frequency of meeting relatives
Social ties	Social Trust	Trust in people (GENERAL)
Social ties	Social Trust	Trust in [RESPONDENT's ETHNIC GROUP] people
Social ties	Social capital	Social capital: who would RESP first ask for help/BORROW MONEY
Social ties	Social capital	Social capital: who would RESP first ask for help/FEELING DISCRIMINATED AGAINST
Social ties	Social capital	Social capital: who would RESP first ask for help/BEING DENIED HEALTH ASSISTANCE
Social ties	Social capital	Social capital: who would RESP first ask for help/NEED FOR LEGAL ASSISTANCE
Social ties	Links/relations with HOME country	Frequency of visits to HOME country/country of ancestors
Social ties	Links/relations with HOME country	Frequency of sending money HOME
Social ties	Social relations	Having friends from same ethnic/minority group as RESPONDENT (YES/NO)
Social ties	Social relations	Having friends from general/majority population (YES/NO)
Social ties	Social relations	Having friends who have a different religion than Respondent
Social ties	Social relations	Having relatives living in the same city
Social ties	Social relations	Having relatives living in other European countries
Social ties	Social relations	Frequency of meeting relatives
Social ties	Social relations	Frequency of talking/interactions/ social networks

Appendix 2: Concepts identified by COST Action WG3 for the conceptual hierarchy of the EMM Survey Registry

Integration Dimensions	Main Topic(s) Covered by the Survey
1. Labour Market	1.13.15.Labour market integration
2. Health	1.13.10.Health/health access
3. Education	1.13.6.Educational attainment/trajectory, human capital, skills
4. Housing/Residential Profile	1.13.9.Housing/housing access 1.13.25.Space use, spatial consequences
5. Income and Poverty	1.13.13.Income-related (and/or poverty)
6. Leisure	1.13.3.Consumption and/or leisure 1.13.26.Time use
7. Language	1.13.16.Language skills/training
8. Religion	1.13.29.Religion
9. Cultural and Social Norms (Pilot 3bis)	1.13.8.Gender relations, gender identity, sexuality 1.13.20.Political inclusion and participation, and social/political attitudes [Take care only of the “social attitudes” and “social values” aspects of this topic.]
10. Legal Status and Rights	1.13.1. Asylum seekers and refugee issues 1.13.2.Citizenship and naturalization 1.13.11.Human smuggling and trafficking 1.13.18.Legal status/administrative situation
11. Belonging and Social Identity (Pilot 3)	1.13.12.Identity (ethnic, national, racial, religious) and belonging
12. Civic Life and Political Participation (Pilot 1)	1.13.20.Political inclusion and participation, and social/political attitudes 1.13.24.Social cohesion and/or civic engagement and/or networks 1.13.27.Transnational patterns (e.g., remittances, travel, engagement with ‘home’ country politics, etc.) and diasporas
13. Stereotypes, Prejudices, and Discrimination (Intergroup Relations/Beliefs) (Pilot 2)	1.13.5.Discrimination, racism, and/or xenophobia 1.13.14.Interethnic contact & conflict 1.13.21.Public attitudes about migration and migrants
14. Demographic flows, patterns, characteristics and behaviours	1.13.4.Demographic characteristics/behaviours 1.13.7.Family reunification, marriage, family relations 1.13.19.Migration trajectory (past/future) 1.13.22. Reasons for migration/migration drivers 1.13.23.Return migration

Appendix 3: Instructions on how to recode variables and use the codebook:

To ensure that the codebook is clear, structured, and user-friendly, we have implemented certain essential steps for inputting recoded variables into the codebook. Please follow these instructions for each variable you recode.

1. First, for each variable, you will need to choose which section it belongs in. Currently, there are 12 sections and an uncategorized section. These sections are preliminary and may be altered at a future date. If you are unsure of which section the variable should go in, please put it in the uncategorized section. All sections should be visible in the sidebar, which also allows you to navigate.
2. First, type the name of the variable (i.e. rasscmbr1). Then, you should select Heading 3 (or the equivalent in the language your Google account is set up in. For instance, in French, it is "Titre 3") in the box to the left of the font choice in the top menu bar. Every variable name should be Heading 3, which will ensure that it is bold, 12-point Times New Roman.
3. Underneath, you should input the following information (as Normal text)
 - a. Variable name - the name from the [Harmonization Sheet](#), should be all lowercase and contain no spaces
 - b. Variable label - a short label for the variable. This may contain spaces, but try to keep it as short as possible. A good rule of thumb is to try to keep labels at or under 30 characters if possible.
 - c. Variable description - a longer description of the variable including what it measures
 - d. Type - refers to whether the variable is string or numeric
 - e. Scale - ONLY FOR NUMERIC VARIABLES - this refers to the scale of the variable (ordinal, binary/dichotomous, interval, etc)
 - f. Values - this is the actual values the variable takes on. Here, you should explain how the values are determined. For example, for intervals you should explain what the high and low values are and what they represent (i.e. 0- Low trust, 1- High trust). When inputting codes, please always put the number followed by a period/full-stop symbol (i.e. 1. Yes)
4. Please refer to [_rasscmbr1](#) for an example of how the above elements should be formatted. You should list each item (Variable name, Variable label) followed by a colon (:) and the corresponding information. There should be a one-line break between Variable description and Type and there should be a line break after Values
5. You should take care to always include the appropriate missing value codes with every variable you add to the codebook, even if it is a string variable. There are 5 potential missing value codes: -995. Not applicable ; -996. Question not asked ; -997. Refused ; -998. Don't know ; -999. Missing
 - a. -995. Not applicable - this should be included any time the question is only posed to a subset of respondents within the questionnaire. This includes instances where a question is conditioned on the response to a previous question. This may also be used for variables that are specific to subnational surveys (i.e. region)
 - b. -996. Question not asked - this should be included in every recoded variable with the exception of the survey characteristic variables. It will be used to indicate that a question was not part of a particular study
 - c. -997. Refused - this should be included if all of the questionnaires that ask the question provide a refusal option
 - d. -998. Don't know - this should be included if all of the questionnaires that ask the question provide a DK option

e. -999. Missing - should always be included, regardless of variable type

Appendix 4: Instructions for generating STATA Do-Files & Recoding

Generic instructions on how to use, store, and share do-files

1. The first time you write Stata Code for a survey series, download the formatted do-file
 - a. The (**) symbol is used to offset permanent title text that should never be altered
 - b. Text offset by (//) is generic text that must be edited based on the variable being coded
 - c. Text offset by /* */ indicates code that you must write
 - d. Annotations within code should be offset by a triple slash (///)
2. Once you have finished coding all variables for that do-file, the do-file should be uploaded to the Preliminary do-file folder. You should notify your supervisor each time a file is added to this folder.
 - a. The do-file should always be named using the following convention:
 - i. Section Name_Sub-section name (if there is one)_your initials_date

Formula to apply when recoding ordinal variables:

For ordinal scales

1. Ordinal scales will be recoded according to a formula so that they take on a value between 0 and 1. Assuming that the low and high values are comparable across all surveys you are harmonizing, then the following formulas should be used
 - a. (For surveys where the lowest possible score is 0): $\frac{\text{response}}{\text{highest value}}$
 - b. (For surveys that begin with 1 as the lowest value): $\frac{(\text{response} - \text{lowest value})}{(\text{highest value} - \text{lowest value})}$
2. If you encounter a situation where one survey goes from agree → to disagree while another goes from disagree → to agree, you will also need to rescale. To do this, you will need to choose the survey for which the high value will become the low value. As a general rule, 'negative' responses such as disagree, dislike, disapprove, etc, should take on the lower values when possible.
 - a. Once you have chosen the survey to rescale, you will apply this formula:
 - i. $\frac{(\text{highest value} - \text{response})}{(\text{highest value} - \text{lowest value})}$

Here is an example:

Survey A provides a 1 → 5 scale that goes from disagree → to agree, whereas Survey B provides a 0-10 scale that goes from agree → to disagree.

Survey A will follow the formula in step 1b:

$$\frac{\text{response} - 1}{5 - 1}$$

so that a response of 1 would take on the value of zero, 2 would become 0.25, and so forth.

Survey B would follow the formula in step 2a. So:

$$\frac{10 - \text{response}}{10 - 0}$$

In this case, a response of 10 (indicating strong disagreement) would take on the value of 0, while 9 would become 0.1 and so forth.

Instructions for writing code

1. Begin by writing the Section number and the Subsection number as text into the do-file
2. Then, write the text START [Variable name]
3. On a new line, write the text [Variable label]
4. Next, write the name of the survey your first source variable comes from.
5. Next, write the code to use the dataset
6. The first recoding step should be to generate the target variable. In the first instance, it should be empty. So you will write `gen targetvariable=. or targetvariable=""`
7. (Only for ordinal scales or categorical variables) Define the value labels for the response options using the 'label define' command. For ordinal scales, you only need to define the 0 and 1 values.
8. Use the *replace* command to change the values of the target variable
9. Use the 'label values' command to assign the value labels to the target variable (where applicable)
10. Assign the variable label using the 'label variable' command
11. Cross-tabulate your original variable and the recoded variable to ensure that the recoding has been made correctly and that all observations are represented
12. Save the data file under a new name
13. Repeat lines 4-12 for each survey for which you must recode a variable
14. To finish, write as text END [Variable name]
15. You should feel free to annotate wherever you see fit. Annotations should use `///` to indicate text.

Instructions for creating the Survey-specific master do-files

You should begin by starting a new do-file, calling/loading the survey, and then continue by copying and pasting the code available in the existing (reviewed do-files in the following order (per codebook sections):

1. Variables identifying studies and respondents
2. Associational membership and civic engagement
3. Non-electoral political behaviors
4. Electoral behaviors
5. Political interest and knowledge
6. Civic & political attitudes and orientations
7. Media use/consumption
8. Identity and belonging
9. Social attitudes and orientations
10. Sociodemographic characteristics
11. Religion
12. Migration Trajectory

You will need to follow the order in which the variables are listed within the subsections of these sections of the codebook. You will note that within the do-files, the sections and subsections are listed (on top) in order to ease your work.

Appendix 5. Codebook of the Postharmonized Dataset on Civic & Political Engagement